

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

Issued to

Shevchenko Valentyna

NO.MANS/2023/01/473

International scientific and practical
conference

„Digital transformation and technologies for
all areas sustainable development of modern
education, science and practice”

26.01.2023

6 hours (0.2 ECTS credits)

PROF. ROMAN ENGLER
Rector

MANS
International University of Applied Sciences
in Lomza

